

Studies on 4, 4'- Dihydroxybenzophenone and its Dimethyl Ether

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4,4'-Dimethoxybenzophenone on chloromethylation gave the 3,3'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative which on oxidation gave the 3,3'-dicarboxylic acid and on Sommelet reaction gave the 3,3'-diformyl derivative. The latter on condensation with 2-hydroxy-and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone gave the corresponding bichalkonyl ketones which on heating with selenium dioxide gave the corresponding biflavonyl ketone. 3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone from Fries migration of 4,4'-diacetoxybenzophenone gave on condensation with benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde the corresponding bichalkonyl ketones which were converted into the corresponding biflavonyl ketones. Bi-(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) ketone has also been synthesised from the 3,3'-diacetyl derivative.

The previous work¹ on the benzophenone derivatives has now been extended to 4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone. On chloromethylation this compound gave a mixture of products from which no pure compound could be isolated. Its dimethyl ether however, on chloromethylation in acetic acid in the presence of zinc chloride gave a di-(chloromethyl) derivative to which the 3,3'-di-(chloromethyl) structure has been assigned as on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate it gave a dicarboxylic acid identical with the one obtained on oxidation of 3,3'-diacetyl-4, 4'-dimethoxybenzophenone. The diacetyl derivative was prepared by the Fries migration of 4,4'-diacetoxybenzophenone and subsequent methylation of the diacetyl derivative formed. The migration product has been assigned the 3,3'-diacetyl structure as it gave a strong colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and its dimethyl ether on oxidation gave a dicarboxylic acid, having the same melting point as 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone-3, 3'-dicarboxylic acid prepared previously by Ishiwata and Takada² by the oxidation of 3,3'-diformyl-4, 4'-dimethoxydiphenylmethane.

The di-(chloromethyl) derivative on reaction with sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished a diacetoxyethyl derivative and on Sommelet reaction it gave the 3,3'-diformyl derivative.

3,3'-Diformyl-4, 4'-dimethoxybenzophenone on condensation with 2-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of ethanolic potash gave bi-(2'-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone (I, R=H). It gave a faint brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and on reaction with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride it afforded a diacetoxy derivative. On refluxing with iso-amylalcohol and selenium dioxide it gave bi-(6'-methoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone (III, R=H). Bi-(6', 7'-dimethoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone (III, R=OCH₃) was similarly synthesised from bi-(2'-hydroxy-4', 6-

1. Balani and Sethna, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 52.

2. Ishiwata and Takada, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1951, **71**, 1254; *C.A.* 1952, **46**, 6101.

dimethoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone (I, R=OCH₃) which in turn was obtained by the condensation of 3,3'-diformyl-4, 4'-dimethoxy benzophenone with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone.

Condensation of 3, 3'-diacetyl-4, 4'-dihydroxy-benzophenone with benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde yielded bi (6'-hydroxy-3'-chalkonyl) (II, R=H) and bi-(4-methoxy-6'-hydroxy-3'-chalkonyl) ketone (II, R=OCH₃) respectively, which on subsequent isomerisation and dehydrogenation gave bi-(6-flavonyl)-(1V, R=H) and bi-(4'-methoxy-6-flavonyl) ketone (IV, R=OCH₃) respectively.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4, 4'-dihydroxybenzophenone on condensation with ethylbromoacetate in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and dry acetone gave 3,3'-diacetyl-4, 4'-dicarboethoxymethoxybenzophenone which on alkaline hydrolysis (10%) gave the corresponding dibasic acid. The acid on refluxing with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride yielded bi-(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) ketone (V).

EXPERIMENTAL*

3,3'-Di(chloromethyl)-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone: On passing dry HCl through a clear mixture of 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone (4.0 g.), zinc chloride (3 g.) formalin (40%; 12 ml.), HCl (10 ml.) and acetic acid (35 ml.) at 85 to 95° for 2 hr., 3,3'-di(chloromethyl) derivative separated. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 150-51°. Yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 60.54; H, 4.66; Cl, 20.58. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3Cl_2$ requires C, 60.17; H, 4.72; Cl, 20.94%.)

The di(acetoxymethyl) derivative: The above di(chloromethyl) derivative (0.5 g.) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate and acetic acid for 1 hr. The product obtained on dilution with water was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 94°. (Found: C, 65.26; H, 5.37; $C_{21}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 65.28; H, 5.7%.)

3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone: A mixture of the above 3,3'-di(chloromethyl) derivative (2.0 g.) hexamine (6.0 g.) and acetic acid (15 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. It was then poured into water (250 ml.) and stirred for 1 hr. Product (0.5 g.) which separated was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 165-66°. (Found: C, 68.45; H, 4.77. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.7%.)

The di-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative: Prepared as usual and crystallised by dissolving in nitrobenzene and precipitating with petroleum ether gave m.p. 311-12° d. (Found: N, 16.83; $C_{29}H_{24}O_4N_8$ requires N, 17.2%.)

3,3'-Dicarboxy-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone: A mixture of the di(chloromethyl) derivative (1.0 g.), $KMnO_4$ (1 g.) and KOH solution (5%; 40 ml.) was warmed on a steam bath for 10 hr. More of $KMnO_4$ (1 g.) was added in small quantities at regular intervals and the acid (0.5 g.) obtained on acidification of the alkaline solution was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 242°. Ishiwata and Takada² reported m.p. 242-43°. (Found: after drying in vacuum at 100° for 4 hr. C, 61.77; H, 4.51. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 61.81; H, 4.24%.)

The same acid was also obtained on alkaline $KMnO_4$ oxidation of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone: A mixture of 4,4'-diacetoxybenzophenone (5 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (8 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 140° for 4 hr. It was decomposed with ice cold HCl and the product was taken up in sodium hydroxide solution. On acidification 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone was obtained. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 182-83°. Yield 2 g. (Found: C, 68.04; H, 4.59. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.73%.) It gave a red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

The diacetoxy derivative: Prepared from the above compound with acetic anhydride in the presence of conc. sulphuric acid, and crystallised from dil. alcohol gave m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 66.37; H, 4.54. $C_{21}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 65.95; H, 4.74%.)

The dimethyl ether. Prepared by refluxing 3, 3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone (3 g.) with dimethyl sulphate (6 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) in acetone for 16 hr. gave m.p. 128°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 70.04; H, 5.32. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.92; H, 5.56%.)

Bi-(2'-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone: To a mixture of 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone (1 g.) and 2-hydroxyacetophenone (2.5 g.) dissolved in sufficient ethanol was added potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. H_2O) and the mixture was left overnight. The product obtained on acidification was washed with water and then with hot alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.5 g.) m.p. 266°. (Found: C, 73.93; H, 4.81. $C_{33}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 74.16; H, 4.53%.) It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The diacetoxy derivative: Prepared as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol.* (Found C, 72.02; H, 4.82. $C_{37}H_{30}O_9$ requires C, 71.83; H, 4.89%.)

Bi-(6'-methoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone: The above chalkone (1 g.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide and iso-amyl alcohol in an oil bath at 140° for 16 hr. It was filtered hot and the product obtained on cooling was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 318-19°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 74.26; H, 4.54. $C_{33}H_{22}O_7$ requires C, 74.71; H, 4.12%.)

Bi-(2'-hydroxy-4', 6-dimethoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone: To 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone (1 g.) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (2.5 g.) in alcohol, KOH (5 g. in 5 ml. H_2O) was added and the clear reaction mixture was kept overnight. It was then acidified and the product obtained was washed with water and then with hot alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.7 g.) m.p. 244-45°. (Found: C, 70.69; H, 5.17. $C_{35}H_{30}O_9$ requires C, 70.69; H, 5.09%.) It gave a very faint brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The diacetoxy derivative: Prepared as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol.* (Found: C, 68.8; H, 5.47. $C_{39}H_{34}O_{11}$ requires C, 69.02; H, 5.01%.)

Bi-(6',7-dimethoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone: A mixture of the above bi-chalkonyl ketone (1 g.), selenium dioxide (4 g.) and iso-amyl alcohol was refluxed for 16 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from chlorobenzene. M.P. 286°d. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 70.82; H, 4.9. $C_{35}H_{26}O_9$ requires C, 71.17; H, 4.4%.)

Bi-(6'-hydroxy-3'-chalkonyl) ketone: KOH (5 g.; in 5 ml. H_2O) was added to a mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone (1 g.) and benzaldehyde (2.5 g.) dissolved in alcohol and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. The chalkone derivative which separated on acidification was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 195-96°. (Found: C, 78.23; H, 4.62. $C_{31}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 78.45; H, 4.67%.) It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The diacetoxy derivative: Prepared as usual and crystallised from alcohol* (Found: C, 75.61; H, 4.60. $C_{35}H_{27}O_7$ requires C, 75.25; H, 4.65%.)

*The diacetoxy derivatives of the bichalkonyls do not give sharp melting point. They soften and then melt over a range of several degrees.

Bi-(6-flavonyl) ketone: Bi-(6'-hydroxy-3'-chalconyl) ketone (1 g.) was refluxed with iso amyl alcohol (15 ml) and selenium dioxide (3 g.) in an oil bath at 140° for 16 hr. It was filtered hot and the product which separated on cooling was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 297-98°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 79.45; H, 4.09. $C_{31}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 79.12; H, 3.85%).

Bi-(4-methoxy-6'-hydroxy-3'-chalconyl) ketone: 3,3'-diacetyl-4, 4'-dihydroxybenzophenone (1 g.) was condensed with anisaldehyde (2.5 g.) in the presence of ethanolic KOH (5 g. in 5 ml. H_2O) and the reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 223°. (Found: C, 73.94; H, 4.59. $C_{33}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 74.16; H, 4.90%). It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The diacetoxo derivative: Prepared as before was crystallised from dil. alcohol.* (Found: C, 71.91; H, 4.98. $C_{27}H_{16}O_9$ requires C, 71.83; H, 4.89%).

Bi-(4'-methoxy-6-flavonyl)ketone: A mixture of the above chalcone (0.5 g.) and selenium dioxide (3 g.) was refluxed in iso amyl alcohol (10 ml.) for 16 hr. at 140°. The product obtained on working up as before was crystallised from xylene. M.P. 273-74°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 74.31; H, 4.23. $C_{33}H_{22}O_7$ requires C, 74.71; H, 4.12%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4, 4'-dicarboethoxymethoxybenzophenone: 3,3'-Diacetyl-4, 4'-dihydroxy benzophenone (1 g.) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (6 g.) and ethyl-bromoacetate (2 ml.) in acetone for 16 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone was crystallised from alcohol. M.P. 116°. Yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 63.68; H, 5.82. $C_{25}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 63.81; H, 5.57%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dicarboxymethoxybenzophenone: The above ester (1 g.) was warmed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (25 ml.; 5%) on a steam bath. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from alcohol and dried in vacuum at 100° for 4 hr. M.P. 125°d. (Found: C, 60.65; H, 4.52. $C_{21}H_{18}O_9$ requires C, 60.87; H, 4.38%).

Bi-(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) ketone: The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (6 ml.) for 45 minutes and then poured into water. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol. M.P. 142-43°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 78.28; H, 4.97. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3$ requires C, 78.62; H, 4.83%).